

JURISPRUDENCE

TYPES OF LABOR CONTRACTS AND CHALLENGES OF EXISTING REGULATION ACCORDING TO THE CURRENT LABOR CODE OF GEORGIA

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Abstract

The current labor legislation of Georgia regulates the types of labor contracts and their characteristic requisites. It is noteworthy that the Labor Code of Georgia provides for both a type of labor contract concluded for a specified period and a type of contract concluded for an indefinite period. Both forms of labor contracts are characterized by certain features, which will be discussed in the following article, however, it should be noted that the Labor Code of Georgia additionally provides for a type of labor contract concluded for a probationary period and Internship Agreement, as a type of labor contract, which is characterized by certain features, the analysis of which is also the subject of interest of this article.

Keywords: Labor law; Labor Code; Contract; Probationary period; Internship; Oral contract; Written contract;

I. Introduction

In any state, the legal regulation of labor relations plays an important role, since in all jurisdictions the well-being and financial security of citizens within the state are largely created at the expense of a functioning labor market, therefore, the proper functioning of the legislation regulating labor relations is a prerequisite for the further development of society. In Georgian reality, according to the current Labor Code, an employment contract is a prerequisite for the origin of labor relations between an employer and an employee³, and labor contracts themselves differ from each other in terms of their execution period or characteristics, which will be discussed in other sections of the article.

It should be noted that an employment contract is an exception to private law contracts, where one party is placed in a subordinate position towards the other party after the conclusion of the contract. An employment contract is concluded based on the free will of both parties, however, labor law restricts the actions of the employer, as the stronger party to the contract.

Accordingly, the employer is obliged to determine the content of the employment contract in such a way that it is fully consistent with the standards of the Labor Code, while the main principle of concluding an employment contract is the free expression of the will of the parties, when the parties can agree on norms that differ from the Labor Code, although the main thing is not to worsen the employee's situation⁴.

In below chapters the forms and types of the labor contracts will be discussed as well as the appropriate characteristics will be analyzed as per current regulations in Georgian Labor Code.

II. Types of Employment Contracts

According to the current Labor Code of Georgia⁵, two types of labor contracts are envisaged, namely, a labor contract concluded for a specified period and a labor contract concluded for an indefinite period, while before the amendments to the Labor Code of Georgia entered into force, the Code also envisaged a labor contract concluded for a specified period of work performance as an independent type of labor contract, which is no longer envisaged by the current Labor Code.

It should be noted that the current Labor Code provides for oral and written labor contracts, i.e., a labor contract concluded for a specified and indefinite period of time can be concluded orally or in writing, although certain rules and standards apply here as well, namely: if the duration of the labor relationship exceeds 1 month, it is necessary to conclude a labor contract in writing, and in the case of a labor relationship concluded for a period of less than 1 month, it is permissible to conclude an oral labor contract between the employee and the employer⁶. The establishment of a written form in the Labor Code serves to protect the rights and interests of the employee and to create legal guarantees for him⁷. The purpose of establishing a mandatory form for an employment contract is to provide clarity and facilitate proof. The employee must be aware of the terms of the contract and, in the event of a dispute, be able to prove both the existence of the contractual relationship and the content of the essential terms of the contract.

The current Labor Code provides for a special rule on when an existing labor relationship between the parties is considered to be concluded for an indefinite period, as well as regulates the standard on what happens when the parties enter into labor relations bypassing the rules prescribed by law. In particular, if

³ Labor Code of Georgia, Article 2

⁴ Beltadze P., Liparteliani R., Commentary on Labor Code of Georgia, Publishing House Samshoblo, Tbilisi, 2018, 6

⁵ Labor Code of Georgia, Article 12

⁶ Labor Code of Georgia, Article 12

⁷ Khajomia T., Commentary on Labor Code of Georgia, Publishing House of New Vision University, Tbilisi, 2023, 125

the term of the labor contract is more than 30 months, or if the labor relationship is continued as a result of concluding a fixed-term labor contract twice or more times and its duration exceeds 30 months, it is considered that a permanent labor contract has been concluded. Fixed-term employment contracts shall be deemed to have been concluded consecutively if the existing fixed-term employment contract was extended immediately upon its expiration or the next fixed-term employment contract was concluded within 60 days of the expiration of the first fixed-term employment contract, and in the event that a fixed-term employment contract is concluded without any grounds provided for by the Labor Code, it shall be deemed to have been concluded as an indefinite employment contract.

Hereby should be as well mentioned that as per labor code of Georgia except when the duration of an employment agreement is 1 year or longer, an employment agreement shall only be concluded for a fixed term if one of the following circumstances are present:

- a) a specific amount of work is to be performed;
- b) seasonal work is to be performed;
- c) the amount of work has temporarily increased;
- d) an employee being temporarily absent from work due to suspended labour relations is being replaced;
- e) the employment agreement provides for the subsidising of wages as defined in the Law of Georgia on Facilitating Employment;
- f) other objective circumstances justifying the conclusion of an employment agreement for a fixed term.

It should also be noted that according to the current Labor Code, a written labor contract is concluded in a language understandable to the parties. A written labor contract may be concluded in several languages. If a written labor contract is concluded in several languages, it must contain a provision regarding which language the labor contract concluded in takes precedence in the event of a discrepancy between the provisions of the labor contracts⁸.

III. Probationary / Trial Period

According to Labor Code of Georgia at the same time with above discussed forms of labor agreement as well is regulated the Probationary Period labor relation that is considered as the independent type of the labor agreement⁹.

Although the labor agreement between the parties for the Trial Period has its purpose and characteristics that differ this type of labor agreement from other types of the labor agreements discussed above and namely: the main purpose of probationary labor agreement is to define the compliance of the candidate with the work requirements¹⁰ - in order to establish the suitability of a person for the work to be performed, by agreement of the parties, an employment agreement for the trial period with a person may be concluded, so that the parties

check and observe during the probation period if the skills and knowledge of the employee for the purposes of the trial period is in full compliance with the work's established needs and obligations.

The labor agreement for the trial period differs from other types of the labor agreement with its characteristics of the form and the period of validity and namely:

a. Trial period can be officially signed between the parties only once for no more than 6 months, otherwise it will not be considered as a labor relation between the parties for the probation purposes, meaning if the agreed relation overcomes the maximum period of 6 months such a trial period relation can be considered as a violation of the labor code of Georgia and the employee can request to define via the court proceedings the labor relations of indefinite period.

b. An employment agreement for a trial period shall be concluded only in writing and in any other circumstance the labor relation existing with between the parties can not be considered as a trial period labor relation.

As per Georgian Labor Code the work performed during a trial period shall be paid for, therefore it is per law defined that the Trial Period is a fee based labor relation and can not be of free of charge nature, that will be a violation of the existing labor regulations.

Hereby, should be noted that the amount of payment and the payment procedure shall be determined by the agreement of the parties.

An employer may, at any time during the trial period, conclude a fixed-term or an open-ended employment agreement with the employee, or terminate the employment agreement for a trial period. Although should be noted that the existence of the trial period not obliges the employer to consequently sign the labor agreement with the party of the probationary labor agreement as the employer is the sole party to define and conclude if the employee of the trial period is good enough for the future needs of the employer and if the candidate can be considered as a competent and able for assignment to labor tasks as an employee of the fixed-term or the indefinite labor agreement.

Hereby, should be noted that as mentioned above the trial period agreement is possible to be signed for maximum 6 months, but the employer can terminate the labor relation at any time with appropriate cause and without prior notice of the employee but the latter shall be remunerated in proportion to the time worked.

IV. Internship

One more type of the labor agreement prescribed and regulated in Labor Code of Georgia is a product of the latest changes into law and namely the Internship

⁸ Labor Code of Georgia, Article 13

⁹ Labor Code of Georgia, Article 17

¹⁰ Chachava S., Gaiparashvili M., Commentary on Labor Code of Georgia, Publishing House of New Vision University, Tbilisi, 2023, 215

Agreement¹¹ regulating labor relations between an intern and the employer and namely: an intern is a natural person who performs for an employer particular work, whether paid or not, in order to upgrade his/her qualifications and to gain professional knowledge, skills or practical experience¹².

Hereby, should be noted that the employer shall not use an intern's labour in order to avoid entering into an employment agreement. An intern shall not replace an employee and employer shall not have the right to hire an intern to replace an employee with whom labour relations were suspended and/or terminated.

At the same time should be mentioned that the duration of unpaid internship shall not exceed 6 months, and the duration of paid internship shall not exceed 1 year. As per the labor code of Georgia the person may do an unpaid internship with the same employer only

once, otherwise will be considered as a violation of employee intern's labor rights.

As for the form of the agreement should be noted that the relations between interns and employers shall be regulated by a written agreement.

V. Conclusion

Taking all above into consideration we may say that the types of labor agreements are well regulated as per Georgian legislation, although from the legal perspective of law drafting techniques could be noted that all types of the labor agreements would be logical to be discussed under one chapter of types of agreements or article in Labor Code of Georgia, although currently the types of labor agreements discussed in this work are well prescribed in labor code of Georgia.

¹¹ Labor Code of Georgia, Article 18

¹² ¹² Chachava S., Gaiparashvili M., Commentary on Labor Code of Georgia, Publishing House of New Vision University, Tbilisi, 2023, 234